

Industry, vocabulary in the field of economy and its analysis

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Abstract: This article describes the importance of learning foreign languages in our country, the necessity of knowing foreign languages in economic relations, how economic neologisms are used.

Key words: 21st century, diplomatic economic relations, term, neologisms.

INTRODUCTION.

Today, in the period of development of science and technology all over the world, the need to learn foreign languages is definitely increasing day by day. A clear example of this is the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to bring the activities of popularization of foreign language learning to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan."

Nowadays, knowledge of foreign languages is becoming very necessary not only for philologists, but also for representatives of all fields. No matter what field you work in, knowing at least 2-3 foreign languages is a must in the 21st century. In today's Uzbekistan, knowledge of English and Russian, along with the mother tongue, will greatly help in the field of specialization and expand the study of achievements in the field. Especially in some cases, when one country signs an economic agreement with another country, or during the establishment of various diplomatic relations and international relations, there is a need for representatives of the field who know foreign languages.

It is known that economy plays an important role in any society. Therefore, the words and terms related to the economy should be clear, concise and logically based.

The rapid development of science and technology has a small impact on the economic sphere, as a result of which new neologisms appear in several economic spheres.

In general, many aspects should be taken into account when adopting international economic words into the Uzbek language. When an economic term enters the Uzbek language, it is necessary to pay attention to its following aspects: compatibility of the term with the sound system of the Uzbek language; whether it has an Uzbek alternative; to the necessity of copying or translation; to the meaning of the economic term; to its simplicity and fluency; to its essence and correctness.

Economic terms entering the Uzbek language from other languages must first be discussed by experts and terminologists, and then approved by the relevant committee of the Oliy Majlis. Only then can such economic terms become legal and can be freely used.

After gaining independence, our country is gradually transitioning to a market economy. The laws of the market economy are being introduced in the society. Neologisms serving the market economy are increasing. A certain part of them is Uzbekized based on the capabilities of our mother tongue, and a certain part is used as an international adaptation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The following cases can be observed in the use of economic terms in the Uzbek language:

1. Many terms have been Uzbekized based on the capabilities of our language. In this case, a group of terms is given with ready-made alternatives in Uzbek language, while a certain part is translated and used, and a part is created based on the rules of the Uzbek language. For example: auction-auction, broker-broker, merchant-trader, commission-broker, commission-brokerage, economy-economy, check or bearer-white check, impersonal check, shareholder-shareholder, businessman-businessman, etc.

2. Another way is to adopt the international terms used in most countries of the world into the Uzbek language. It should be noted here that it is difficult to find an Uzbek alternative to all the new terms. Therefore, most of them are used in their original form in the languages of most countries of the world, and this use is convenient for the exchange of information among businessmen of the world. For example: corruption, credit, export, grant, auditor, contract, currency, lease, manager, license, businessman, non-resident.

Below are some terms that are widely used in the field of economics. Some of these words are Uzbek words, and some of them are directly imported from other languages and are used in our language.

DISCUSSION

AUKSION - (lat.auction) - "auction" sale, open sale. This trading service buys the product to the highest bidder.

BANK - collects funds of legal entities and individuals depending on the time and ensures continuous circulation, loans to enterprises and money checks in general, mediates in court, parties' performance payment and other settlement works, golden check credit and financial institution that performs operations related to the national currency. B. paying depositors a percentage of the information, charging borrowers a continuing interest rate, and there is a bank profit that varies by these percentages.

BIZNES- (English business-ish, activity, occupation) wealth, profit-oriented work, activity. Businesses are divided into large, medium and small types depending on the scale of operation. It is divided according to the average number of employees and the volume of products.

BIZNESMEN - (English business-ish, man-adam) - a person engaged in business, a businessman.

BIRJA - (Goll.beurs, German. Borse-wallet)- 1) an organization that actively participates in the exchange of products, currency and securities, as well as in the implementation of accounting and information services. Receives a brokerage fee for providing services; 2) a place where the stock market is traded.

BOJ- (Arab.-tribute, tax) - money levies levied by the state on goods, property and valuables transported across the country's border under customs control.

BROKER - (engl.broker) - an official broker between sellers and buyers of products, securities, currency. A person who has the right to enter into agreements and contracts on behalf of himself or clients.

VALYUTA - (ital. valuta. lat. valere- value, value) - means of payment equal to the currency of the country and its type (gold, silver, paper, money).

VEKSEL - (German: Wechsel, exact exchange) - a special form of valuable paper given in writing regarding debt obligations. the lending party has the right to claim the debt at the end of the period specified in the promissory note.

IMPORT - (lat. importo-kiritaman) - 1) foreign products brought from abroad for use or sale in the country; 2) capital I.- capital coming to the country from abroad (loan, bond, etc.); 3) total number and value of imported products.

INVESTISIYA - (nem. investitlion, lat. investire- to dress)- investment by an investor to implement a certain activity, to introduce capital funds, investments, to spend in order to gain profit. I. can be made in the country (domestic investment) and in foreign countries (external investment). Finance I.si- includes the purchase of valuable securities, accumulation of funds, etc., investments spent on real material production.

IPOTEKA - (greek.hypotheke-garov)- pledging a certain real estate (land, building, etc.) to get a loan.

LISENZIYA - (lat. licentia-freedom, right)- permission; 1) a permit issued by state authorities to import or export goods from foreign countries; 2) the right to use something with light conditions or free of charge; 3) reduction of customs fees for the export or import of goods from the border. Patented L.- registration and granting to others the right to use the invention for which the certificate was issued.

PATENT - (lat. patens-certificate, label)- 1) a certificate allowing to engage in some type of business in a private way, issued by financial authorities on the basis of relevant documents; 2) a certificate of authorship of a scientific discovery and invention. P. will be patented by the state.

POLIS - (fr.police, ital, pollissa-tilkhat) - a document about the conclusion of a personal or property insurance contract and its conditions.

REKLAMA - (fr.reclame) - unbiased information about goods or services, to convey to buyers their properties, advantages and conditions of purchase in order to sell them more. R. is carried out through special firms and is a source of high income.

SERTIFIKAT - (fr.certifikat-I confirm, I testify) is a witnessing document. For example: auditor's certificate - a document confirming the correctness of the declared balance sheet of the company. Insurance certificate is a document that records the terms of the insurance contract. Shareholding certificate is a document confirming that its owner owns a part of the company's (company's) capital. Certificate of quality of goods in foreign economic relations, etc.

As a result of the improvement of the mechanisms of the market economy in our country, all forms of private ownership are developing, opening a wide path to entrepreneurship, as a result, trade with foreign countries, i.e., export-import work is being carried out. In this regard, it is very important to know a foreign language, in particular, we need to understand economic neologisms. In this regard, let's recall the speech of the first President of our Republic, I.A. Karimov:

CONCLUSION

"For the implementation of socio-political, spiritual and economic reforms of our country, the service of a foreign language is great in preparing intelligent, well-rounded national personnel with world-class education."

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